

(Table 1). A similar trend was found when these varieties were tested under the different climatic conditions of the All India Coordinated Rice Physiology program.

Short- and medium-duration varieties performed better in the dry season (65% HD grains) than in the wet season (45-55%).

HD grains had a negative relationship with higher N levels in the field (Table 2). However, higher N

Table 1. Grain grade index of early, medium, and late varieties by season. Andhra Pradesh, India, 1984.

Variety	Grain grade index (%)	
	Wet season	Dry season
<i>Early</i>		
Rasi	50	62
Ratna	45	60
Sita	52	59
<i>Medium</i>		
Jaya	55	64
Prakash	58	65
<i>Late</i>		
IETS 656	71	77
Mahsuri	70	75
CR1009	65	70
Pankaj	75	80
<i>Angular transformation</i>		
CD 5% =	2.33	2.00
CD 1% =	3.21	2.75
CV (%) =	2.64	2.01

levels resulted in higher production of tillers, panicles, and spikelets, and higher leaf area index and total dry

matter. Those overall increased yields were attributed to other yield components. □

Table 2. Influence of N level on grain grade index and yield components of 3 varieties. Andhra Pradesh, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Tillers/m ²	Panicles/m ²	Leaf area index	Total dry matter (g/m ²)	Spikelets/m ²	Grain index (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Ratna</i>							
0	546	526	3.4	1,415	34,350	60	5.8
50	603	573	5.0	1,464	38,800	57	6.4
100	605	590	5.1	1,582	43,120	56	6.8
150	609	569	6.0	1,586	52,950	56	6.8
200	620	585	5.9	1,590	54,530	46	6.9
Experimental mean	596.6	568.6	5.08	1,526.33	44,750	55.00	6.54
CD 5%	6.4	5.5	0.54	17.66	2,290	3.45	0.62
CD 1%	9.3	8.0	0.79	25.68	3,210	5.38	ns
CV (%)	0.6	0.5	5.67	0.61	3.32	3.33	5.00
<i>Prakash</i>							
0	550	543	8.3	1,516	31,400	56	6.1
50	563	551	8.8	1,662	34,990	59	6.3
100	589	581	7.6	1,685	38,060	48	6.8
150	635	624	7.6	2,896	38,270	42	6.1
200	688	674	10.2	3,007	39,100	40	6.9
Experimental mean	605.0	594.6	8.5	2,153.20	36,364	49.00	6.6
CD 5%	6.4	7.74	0.21	23.81	1,504	5.38	0.4
CD 1%	9.4	11.3	0.31	34.63	2,109	7.83	0.6
CV (%)	0.6	0.69	1.34	0.59	2.69	5.83	3.2
<i>Phalguna</i>							
0	409	401	4.3	1,462	24,500	56	5.7
50	435	412	6.7	1,602	22,240	58	6.8
100	468	433	6.8	1,679	23,910	54	7.0
150	479	473	6.4	1,694	23,230	53	7.1
200	490	475	6.2	1,696	35,380	50	7.3
Experimental mean	456	439	6.1	1,627	25,852	54	6.8
CD 5%	11	7	0.5	23.2	1,683	4	0.5
CD 1%	16	10	0.8	34	2,359	ns	0.8
CV (%)	1	1	4.6	1.8	4	4	4.2

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DISEASE RESISTANCE

Reaction of IR lines to tungro virus (RTV)

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We screened 51 breeding lines against RTV, using artificial inoculation in the glasshouse. The seedlings (15 d after seeding) were exposed to green leafhoppers (GLH) that had acquisition access feeding on RTV-infected TN1 plants for 4 d, at 2 insects/ seedling. The insects were

allowed 2 d inoculation access feeding. RTV infection was scored 15 d after inoculation, following the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (Table 1).

Ten seedlings of each culture scoring 0-3 were tested for serological reaction to RTBV and RTSV by latex agglutination method (serum supplied by H. Hibino, IRRI). Reactions of all 10 seedlings in each culture were similar (Table 2).

Breeding lines IR32429-148-1-3-3, IR35366-90-3-2-1-2, IR37865-29-3-1-3, and IR39357-91-3-2-3 are being evaluated and used for breeding resistant varieties. □

Table 1. RTV infection in IRRI rice cultures.

Selection	RTV % ^a	Grade
IR42	18	4
IR24632-34-2	60	7
IR25588-7-3-1	75	8
IR25840-83-3-2	50	7
IR28128-45-3-3-2	38	6
IR29658-43-3-2-1	46	7
IR29670-15-2-3	25	5
IR29692-99-3-2-1	18	4
IR29725-109-1-2-1	13	4
IR31802-48-2-2-2	31	6
IR31851-96-2-3-2-1	58	7
IR31868-64-2-3-3-3	30	5
IR32307-107-3-2-2	67	8
IR32429-47-3-2-2	44	7
IR32429-68-3-3-3	50	7
IR32429-122-3-1-2	50	1
IR32429-148-1-3-3	0	0

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Table 1 continued.

Selection	RTV % ^a	Grade
IR32843-92-2-2-3	40	6
IR32851-87-2-3-1	56	7
IR34631-79-2-2-3	46	7
IR35293-125-3-2-3	15	4
IR35366-28-3-1-2-2	54	7
IR35366-90-3-2-1-2	0	0
IR35546-17-3-1-3	36	6
IR35546-33-2-2-3	33	6
IR37865-29-3-1-3	10	3
IR39357-91-3-2-3	10	3
IR39357-133-3-2-2-3	60	7
IR39379-99-2-3-2-3	69	4
IR39385-20-1-2-1-1	25	5
IR39385-124-3-3-2-3	18	4
IR41985-111-3-2-2	80	8
IR42015-83-2-2-2	38	6
IR39379-190-2-2-3-1	17	4
IR39422-18-1-2-2	75	8
IR25604-99-1-3-2-2	18	4
IR39422-19-3-3-3-3	60	7
IR39423-124-3-3-1	46	7
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	54	7
IR28150-84-3-3-2	21	5
IR28222-9-2-2-2-2	46	7
IR28224-3-2-3-2	72	8
IR28228-28-1-3-3-2	29	5
IR28228-119-2-3-1-1	18	4
IR29723-143-3-2-1	53	7
IR31836-46-1-3-1	62	8
IR32453-93-3-3-1-3	40	6
IR32720-138-2-1-1-2	70	8
IR34583-22-1-2	62	8
IR39326-9-2-2-3	62	8
IR39334-31-2-2-2	42	7
ADT36 (susceptible check)	90	9
ADT31 (susceptible check)	80	8
TN1 (susceptible check)	90	9
TKM9 (susceptible check)	100	9
IET7492 (resistant check)	8	3

^aOne hundred seedlings/culture inoculated.

Table 2. Serological reaction of RTV-resistant cultures.^a

Selection	Reaction ^b to	
	RTBV	RTSV
IR32429-148-1-3-3	-	-
IR35366-90-3-2-1-2	-	-
IR37865-29-3-1-3	-	-
IR39357-91-3-2-3	+	-
IR50 (resistant check)	+	-
ET7492 (local resistant check)	-	+
TKM9 (susceptible check)	++	++
ADT36 (susceptible check)	+	+++

^aTen seedlings/culture tested. ^b - = no infection, + = low infection, ++ = medium infection, +++ = high infection.

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Field screening for blast (Bl) resistance

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Bl caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* is a major disease affecting commonly grown varieties IR50 and TKM9 during Dec-Feb throughout Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu. A severe outbreak occurred during 1985-86.

To identify a resistant, high-yielding rice culture for this season, we evaluated 93 rice accessions under nursery conditions when disease pressure was high. Seeds were sown in 1.2- × 3.0-m plots. Diammonium phosphate (DAP), applied at 180 g/plot 10 d after sowing, induced severe incidence of Bl. Disease scoring was done at 30 d after sowing according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Among the cultures or varieties tested, 38 showed resistant reactions of 1-3, 21 had 5, others showed 7-9 (see table). Most of the highly susceptible cultures had IR50 as one parent. □

Reaction of rice accessions to Bl at Tirur, India.

Culture or variety	Parentage	Disease score ^a
BG367-3	BG280-1-2/Ptb 33	1
TM10265	ADT31/IR8	1
TM4865	AC76/IR8	1
DPI 1091/5	IR20/Kannagi	1
IR20	IR262/TKM 6	1
IR52		1
IR54		1
IR62		1
TNAU843136	CO 37/IR8	1
TNAU831549	TNAU1756/Bhavani	1
TNAU831358	CO 37/Pankhari 203	1
TNAU831411	IET2508/TNAU1756	1
TNAU831399	IET6262/CO 37	1
TNAU831434	IET6262/TNAU1756	1
TM8089	Selection from TKM9	3
ADT36	Triveni/IR20	3
TM1304	TKM 9 Mutant (10 kr)	3
TM1305	TKM 9 Mutant (10 kr)	3
TM1313	TKM 9 Mutant (10 kr)	3
TM1314	TKM 9 Mutant (10 kr)	3
CO 34	TN1/CO 29	3
AS25370	ASD1/IRON 207	3
AS28883	TKM9/IR36	3
IR36	IR1561//IR24-4/ <i>O. nivara</i> ///CR94-13	3
IR56		3
IR60		3
TNAU80030	IR30/Babawee// IR2703-1-252	3

Table continued.

Culture or variety	Parentage	Disease score ^a
TNAU80042	R. Heenathi/ R3403-267 ²	3
TNAU801804	CO 41/CO 39	3
TNAU831540	Pankhari 203/IR36	3
TNAU831521	PY2/IR36	3
TNAU831345	CO 37/IR34	3
TNAU831351	CO 37/SLO 16	3
TNAU843062	IET4141/CO 43	3
TNAU843032	CO 41/CO 43	3
TNAU843028	PY1/CO 43	3
TNAU83134	IET2508/TKM9	3
TNAU840337	TKM9/W. Ponni	3
TM4660	ADT3 1/CH46	5
AS13744	ADT3 1/Ratna// ASD8/IR8	5
TM1307	TKM9 Mutant (10 kr)	5
TNAU801790	CO 41/CO 39	5
TKM1	Pisini pureline selection	5
TNAU83077	CO 73/IR50	5
TNAU83054	IR50/TKM9	5
TNAU8306911	IR50/Kannagi	5
TNAU83069/2	IR50/Kannagi	5
TNAU801803	CO 41/CO 39	5
TNAU83104	CO 41/CO 39	5
TNAU83108	TKM9/TNAU658	5
TNAU831520	PY2/IR36	5
TNAU842955	TKM9/W. Ponni	5
TNAU843232	IET6262/CO 37	5
TNAU831541	TNAU1756/Bhavani	5
TNAU2151	IR28/Kannagi	5
TNAU2099	GEB24/IR30	5
TNAU2057	CO 37/IR26	5
TNAU840335	TKM9/W. Ponni	5
TNAU840336	TKM9/W. Ponni	5
TM2011	C22/TKM6//IR50	7
TM2017	C22/TKM6//IR50	7
TM2021	C22/TKM6//IR50	7
TM2022	TKM9/TKM1//ADT36	7
TM2025	TKM9/TKM1//ADT36	7
TM2026	TKM9/TKM1//ADT36	7
TM9400	IR8/Kalinga// IR34/CH1039	7
CO 33	IR8/ADT27	7
TNAU801793	CO 41/CO 39	7
TKM5	Manakattai PLS	7
TKM6	GEB24/CO 18	7
TKM7	Kullakar PLS 1	7
TKM8	TKM6/TN1	7
IR8	Peta/DGWG	7
TNAU80058	IR2061-456-1-55/IR36	7
TNAU2209	CO 33/CO 13	7
TNAU801824	CO 41/CRM13-3241	7
TM1324	TKM 9 Mutant (20 kr)	9
TM1325	TKM 9 Mutant (20 kr)	9
TM1326	TKM 9 Mutant (20 kr)	9
TKM9	TKM7/IR8	9
IR50		9
TM4966	TKM8/ADT9//CR141- 192/IR26	9
Kannagi	IR8/TKM6	9
TKM4	Yerra Sona PLS	9
CO 18	Vellaikar PLS	9
TNAU840193	9426/6/IR50	9
TNAU840198	9426/6/IR50	9
TNAU842805	94-26/6/IR50	9
TNAU831146	20060/2/IR50	9
TNAU2006	CO 13/IR50	9
TNAU831154	CO41/IR50	9
TNAU831126	TNAU2426/2/IR50	9
TNAU840230	CO 41/IR50	9

^a Standard evaluation system for rice.